

Image Captioning Using Deep Learning and CNN

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Abstract— *In this seminar paper, we thoroughly explore the labeled images with the goal of connecting visual content with human language, ultimately offering informative and captivating descriptions for images. This paper thoroughly investigates the importance of image captioning and the critical mechanisms involved. Our approach utilizes a pre-trained ResNet50 for extracting image features and incorporates a sequential model based on LSTM for creating detailed image descriptions.*

Keywords- CNN, deep learning, LSTM

I. INTRODUCTION

Our main goal is not only to make images visible to computers, but also to explain them in a way that is easily understood by humans. The allusion of this technology are broad, from helping visually impaired individuals to facilitating visual recognition.

We take advantage of the capabilities of the pre-trained ResNet50 image, which allows the computer to interpret complex images. At the same time, our model incorporates an (Long Short-Term Memory) LSTM-based architecture, which guides the computer to generate a consistent, context-sensitive description. We will conduct an in-depth exploration of the model's internal mechanisms, encompassing everything from data preparation to the complex training procedures

In the final stages, we will unveil the results and showcase the capabilities of our system. Additionally, we will delve into the potential applications of this technology and the transformative role it plays in enhancing the computers comprehension of the world that surrounds us.

II. RELATED WORKS

Deep learning approaches have attracted considerable attention from researchers in the field of picture captioning. Johnson et al.'s study [1], which used a convolutional neural network (CNN) and a recurrent neural network (RNN) combination to generate image captions, is one of the notable papers in this field. Their strategy emphasizes how deep learning can improve comprehension of visual content. not as a stand-alone document, but rather the entire proceedings.

The advent of large-scale image datasets, such as flickr8k[2], has accelerated progress in image captioning. These datasets serve as valuable resources for training and evaluating captioning models. The presence of diverse images with associated descriptions has become a cornerstone for benchmarking image captioning systems.

Transfer learning has emerged as a crucial technique in the field of image captioning. Researchers like Xu et al. [3] have explored the utilization of pre-trained models, such as InceptionV3 and ResNet, for feature extraction and fine-tuning. Employing transfer learning has not only enhanced the efficiency of captioning models but has also increased their adaptability to diverse visual domains.

The "Show and Tell" concept, a model that integrates Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks for generating captions, was initially introduced in the work by Vinyals et al. [4]. This approach has significantly influenced the advancement of image captioning systems.

III. METHODOLOGY

The central objective of this research is to enable computers to understand images and generate precise and descriptive captions. The selected methodology for image captioning is meticulously designed to bridge the gap between visual content and human language.

A. Data Collection and Preprocessing

i.Dataset:

We made use of the Flickr8k dataset, which is accessible on Kaggle, to build our dataset. This dataset comprises a significant archive of photographs and has found extensive application in studies centered around image captioning. It encompasses a diverse array of photos; each being accompanied by one or more comprehensive captions. For our research, we concentrated on a carefully chosen subset of images derived from this dataset.

ii.Data Split

To ensure that the training and analysis of model is accurate and reliable, divided the data sets into two subsets: the training set and the validation set, split 80% of the data for training and the remaining 20 % for validation. Followed a common practice of an 80-20 split. This method is important for the evaluate of the power of the model. It provides the means to evaluate the performance of the model in other samples, thereby verifying its reliability and efficiency.

iii.Image preprocessing

In this study, we performed a series of image preprocessing steps necessary to ensure that our image subject model matched the standard data These preprocessing procedures include:

- Image Resize: Images in flickr8k dataset were converted to a constant resolution of 224x224 pixels. These changes were important to ensure uniform size which enhanced efficiency in model.
- Extraction of image features: We used the power of pre-trained ResNet50 images to extract valuable image features.
- Normalization: Before inputting the images into our model, we applied image normalization using the VGG16 preprocessing function.

B. Model Architecture

The architecture for this project revolves around the realm of graphical reference, and serves as an important bridge between computer vision and natural language processing. The process begins with ResNet50, a consumed model the highly acclaimed former trainer known for his use of high-quality self-extraction techniques. This process involves a variety of techniques including hiding text and combining image and text components through merging. To further enhance the performance of the model, dense layers are combined with batch normalization.

During the training phase, categorical cross-entropy is employed as the loss function, working in tandem with the Adam optimizer. This combination plays a fundamental role in optimizing the model's performance.

C. Model Training

This section delves into the model training process, where it defined earlier is fine-tuned to generate meaningful captions for images. The training involves an LSTM-based sequence model fed with both image features and previously generated text. It explores details such as data preprocessing, loss functions, optimizer choice, and training metrics. The model undergoes training over several epochs, and the progress is visualized through accuracy and loss plots.

D. Model Evaluation

The "Model Evaluation" part evaluates the trained image captioning model's performance in a critical manner. It focuses on assessing the model's capacity to come up with captions for brand-new pictures.

Fig1: Image for generating caption

Fig2: Generated caption

IV. BUILD MODEL

Building a deep learning model for image captioning using CNN requires a combination of software tools and frameworks, typically Python along with libraires like TensorFlow, Keras, and others for data handling. Below is a step-by-step guide to creating a simple CNN model for this task using TensorFlow and Keras

A. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
[ ] import os
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from keras.preprocessing.image import load_img, img_to_array
import keras
import sys, time, os, warnings
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import string
import progressbar
from collections import Counter
from copy import copy
from keras.models import Model
from tensorflow.keras.applications import ResNet50
from keras.applications.vgg16 import preprocess_input
from collections import OrderedDict
from keras.preprocessing.sequence import pad_sequences
from tensorflow.keras.utils import to_categorical
from keras.preprocessing.text import Tokenizer
warnings.filterwarnings("ignore")
```

B. Prepare the data set

```
## combined model for decoder
decoder = layers.add([ftxt, fimage2])
decoder = layers.Dense(256, activation='relu')(decoder)
droplayer1 = layers.Dropout(0.5)(decoder)
BN = layers.BatchNormalization()(droplayer1)
output = layers.Dense(vocab_size, activation='softmax')(BN)
model = models.Model(inputs=[input_image, input_txt], outputs=output)

model.compile(loss='categorical_crossentropy', optimizer='adam', metrics = ['accuracy'])

print(model.summary())
```

V. RESULT

The image captioning generator relies on CNN and LSTM for generating a short description of image. The models were trained using a dedicated dataset, flickr8k dataset. BLEU is a popular metric for assessing the quality of generated text. The code segregates the results into two categories: "pred_good" and "pred_bad," based on the BLEU score. Predictions with high BLEU scores (> 0.5) are considered "pred_good," while those with low BLEU scores (< 0.2) are categorized as "pred_bad." This categorization helps identify the quality of the generated captions.

VI. CONCLUSION

Image captioning using deep learning techniques explore the development and evaluation of a model capable of generating

textual descriptions for images. Image captioning using CNN (Convolutional Neural Networks) and deep learning is a powerful technology that enables computers to understand images and describe them in human-like language. By combining CNN for image understanding and deep learning models like LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) for generating captions, we bridge the gap between visual content and natural language. This has various practical applications, from assisting the visually impaired to improving image search and organization. It's a promising area of research that continues to advance the capabilities of AI in understanding and communicating about visual information.

VII. REFERENCES

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